

The variability of students' EFL vocabulary knowledge: EFL proficiency, type of high school and the length of learning English

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The current study aimed to explore receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge among 278 ($N = 278$) freshmen EFL students in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Their vocabulary knowledge was measured by *Vocabulary Levels Tests* targeting words that belong to 2000, 3000 and 5000 frequency levels. This vocabulary knowledge was assessed in relation to a few factors, namely, the self-rated overall English proficiency, the average EFL grade during elementary and high school, the type of high school attended, and the length of formal EFL learning. The students achieved much higher scores on the receptive than productive knowledge measure, the former ranging from $M = 9.94$ to $M = 13.95$, and the latter from $M = 4.45$ to $M = 8.78$, with the gap between receptive and productive scores being the greatest between scores for 3000 frequency level words. The results of MANOVA and ANOVA statistical tests showed that all the aforementioned factors, except for the length of learning English, significantly impacted both receptive and productive EFL vocabulary knowledge. This study is expected to significantly contribute to current understanding of EFL learning, and vocabulary knowledge development as its integral part, in the Global South context. It will offer both students and teachers a valuable assessment of the current situation, along with practical guidelines for further improvement in this respect.

Keywords: English GPA; Productive Vocabulary Knowledge; Receptive Vocabulary Knowledge; Self-Rated Knowledge; Type of High School

1. Introduction

After decades of grammar primacy, vocabulary started attracting greater research interest (González Fernández & Schmitt, 2017; Meara, 1995) and was even considered a prerequisite for grammar acquisition (Malvern et al., 2008). It has been proven to correlate strongly with overall language proficiency

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(Masrai & Milton, 2021; Miralpeix & Munoz, 2018; Waring & Nation, 2004) and the development of different language skills (Enayat & Derakhshan, 2021; Meara, 1996; Nation, 2001). Despite its acknowledged importance, the development of vocabulary knowledge remains relatively under-researched (Heidari, 2019), and learners frequently struggle to reach a vocabulary size of few thousands (Nation, 2022). While well-educated adult native speakers are estimated to know around 17000 base words (Goulden et al., 1990), second language (L2) learners who demonstrate the knowledge of 2000 most frequent words are expected to be able to follow around 90% of spoken language (Nation, 2001). Furthermore, the knowledge of 3000 most frequent words warrants that they will be able to understand unsimplified texts (Laufer, 1992) while the knowledge of 5000 most frequent words enables them to enjoy reading in the target language (Hirsh & Nation, 1992).

In addition to the quantity of vocabulary knowledge, its quality should be taken into consideration. It has become clear that gaining vocabulary knowledge is an incrementing process which develops gradually and encompasses different layers of mastery (Henriksen, 1999; Schmitt, 1998, 2000; Schmitt & Schmitt, 2020). For instance, Henriksen (1999) analyses vocabulary knowledge along three continua: (a) partial to precise, (b) shallow to deep, and (c) receptive to productive—the first two reflecting the comprehension of word knowledge, and the third one indicating access to word knowledge and its use. On the other hand, Nation (2001) proposes three types of vocabulary knowledge: the knowledge of (a) form, (b) meaning, and (c) use, and within each of these categories, he distinguishes between receptive and productive knowledge. Regarding the receptive-productive dichotomy, it remains disputable whether they represent opposite poles or a continuum (Laufer & Goldstein, 2004). While some (e.g., Lee, 2024; Meara, 1997) perceive them as different types of knowledge that do not directly lead into each other, the majority (e.g., Faerch et al., 1984; Webb & Nation, 2017) reckon that vocabulary knowledge transitions gradually from receptive to productive. Still, they seem to be strongly related constructs (Lee, 2024; Zhong, 2018) that we need to have in mind when both teaching and learning a language.

In general, receptive vocabulary knowledge entails completing tasks through receptive language skills—i.e., reading and listening—while productive vocabulary knowledge underlies students' speaking and writing skills (Laufer & Goldstein, 2004; Nation, 1990). Although receptive knowledge refers to the ability to recognize or have passive knowledge, and productive to the ability to use words correctly or active knowledge (Pignot-Shahov, 2012), they have been operationalized differently. Receptive knowledge has been considered as the knowledge enabling one to translate words from L2 to L1 (Waring, 1997), to retrieve the word form (Laufer et al., 2004), to recognize the form, define it or find its synonym (Webb, 2008); productive vocabulary knowledge has been

defined as the knowledge used when translating words from L1 into L2 (Waring, 1997), retrieving word meaning (Laufer et al., 2004), or recalling the word form and meaning (Webb, 2008).

A slightly different approach to conceptualizing receptive and productive knowledge was offered by Laufer et al. (2004), who introduced two criteria for assessing the quality of knowledge, the first one based on the distinction between active (productive) and passive (receptive) knowledge or the retrieval of form and meaning, and the second one related to the difference between recall and recognition. They distinguished between learners who can recall the form and meaning of a word when needed and those who cannot but can recognize it among other options. Thus, they proposed the following types of vocabulary knowledge:

- (a) active recall, when students can provide the target word in a meaningful context, with a few initial letters provided as cues to eliminate the use of other structures;
- (b) passive recall, when students are able to complete a sentence with a meaningful structure without any cues, allowing more options;
- (c) active recognition, referring to the ability to recognize the word defined; and
- (d) passive recognition, relating to the ability to recognize the correct definition of the target word among different options.

The authors suggest that word knowledge gradually develops from passive recognition, representing the lowest level of familiarity with the meaning of the target word, to active recall, being the highest degree of knowledge (Laufer et al., 2004).

Regardless of the approach to receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge, authors generally agree that receptive knowledge exceeds (Fan, 2000; Laufer, 1998; Laufer & Goldstein, 2004; Laufer & Paribakht, 1998; Lee, 2024; Melka, 1997; Tschirner, 2004; Waring, 1998; Webb, 2008; Zhong & Hirsh, 2009) and precedes (Aitchison, 1994; Channell, 1988; Melka, 1997) productive knowledge. At lower stages, receptive knowledge develops more rapidly, and although productive knowledge begins to increase at a faster rate, it hardly ever reaches the level of receptive knowledge. The question that arises is how the process of both active and passive vocabulary knowledge development can be accelerated in different foreign language contexts. Further studies are needed in this respect, as the relationship between receptive and productive knowledge still remains debatable (Schmitt, 2014).

Firstly, an analysis of the current situation in the given setting should be carried out to raise both students' and teachers' awareness of the importance of both quality and quantity of vocabulary knowledge. There is a lack of such investigations in many English as a foreign language (EFL) settings within the Global South (Pennycook & Makoni, 2020) including Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H) where, to our knowledge, no similar study has been conducted. Secondly, based on the research findings, necessary guidelines should be offered to all individuals directly or indirectly involved in language education, particularly teachers who are in need of expert assistance in realizing all segments of their job ranging from planning, organizing, training and testing to teaching (Nation, 2021).

Therefore, the current study aimed to explore the receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge of Bosnian EFL students in their first year of university—i.e., after their elementary and high school education. Their vocabulary knowledge was assessed and compared in relation to their self-rated overall knowledge of English and their average English language grade to determine the importance attributed to vocabulary knowledge and to identify which type is considered more important when assessing the overall English proficiency. Furthermore, the study also explored the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and the type of high school, to determine whether the context of formal language learning is influential regardless of equal opportunities for informal language learning. Additionally, the importance of the duration of formal learning was analyzed as two groups were involved—those who had been learning English officially for five to eleven years, and those who had been learning it for more than twelve years. This study is expected to contribute to the current understanding of EFL learning in the Global South context, with a focus on vocabulary knowledge development as its integral part. It aims to provide both students and teachers with a valuable assessment of the current situation and useful guidelines for further improvement in this respect.

2. Background

The disparity in vocabulary knowledge, both in quality and quantity, among learners has been a focal point of research interest for many years. High school graduates who are native English speakers typically demonstrate knowledge of approximately 20000 word families (Nation, 1990). In contrast, the vocabulary knowledge of high school and university EFL students worldwide tends to be much more limited, averaging around 3000 word families, albeit with significant variations. For example, Nurweni and Read (1999) discovered that Indonesian university students in their study knew about 1200 word families. Similarly, Laufer (1998) found that Israeli high school students had a receptive knowledge of 3500 word families and a productive knowledge of

2550. Further research by Barrow et al. (1999) into Japanese university students' vocabulary knowledge revealed a range between 2000 and 3000 word families. Harji et al. (2015) reached a similar conclusion in the Malaysian context, showing that undergraduate students from three academic programs demonstrated knowledge of only 2000-word frequency level. Tang (2007) further confirmed these findings by showing that EFL students in elementary school demonstrated knowledge of approximately 925 words, while high school students knew around 2891 words. However, Staehr (2008) conducted research on Danish learners of English aged 15-16, and found that even 77% of the participants did not demonstrate knowledge of 2000 most frequent English words.

The comparison of students' receptive and productive vocabulary sizes has been a subject of a plethora of studies worldwide (e.g., Fan, 2000; Laufer, 1998; Laufer & Paribakht; Morgan & Oberdeck, 1930). In terms of L1, students' receptive knowledge is believed to be five (Chamberlain, 1965) or four (Hartmann, 1946) levels higher than their productive knowledge. However, among L2 speakers, the gap between the two types of vocabulary knowledge appears to be smaller, passive knowledge being double the size of active vocabulary knowledge (Eringa, 1974). Still, some studies have shown that the gap between them might be comparable to the gap existing in the native language. For instance, conducting one of the first enquiries comparing the two types of vocabulary knowledge among German university level students, Morgan and Oberdeck (1930) concluded that receptive knowledge superseded productive by five levels of word frequency. A smaller but still great gap between these two types of vocabulary knowledge was revealed in Hajiyeva's (2014) study, conducted among first-year students in the EFL context of Azerbaijan. On the receptive vocabulary assessment, the participants scored an average of 16.8 out of 30 at the 2000 frequency level, 11.7 at the 3000 frequency level, and 7.8 at the 5000 frequency level. The results from the productive vocabulary tests were much lower, with scores ranging from 0.6 out of 18 at the 5000 frequency level to 5.7 out of 18 at the 2000 frequency level. In fact, Fan (2000) indicated that the relationship between receptive and productive knowledge is not straightforward but rather inconsistent, being largely dependent on the learner's environment. The author found out that the gap was smaller among those students who engaged actively in vocabulary learning within and outside the school setting. Laufer and Paribakht (1998) suggested that the difference in vocabulary knowledge might be more pronounced among second language than foreign language learners, the latter being more exposed to formal language learning resulting in deeper knowledge of the word form and meaning than in incidental learning conditions. It takes some time for incidental learning effects to be visible. In this particular study, the gap between active and passive knowledge among L2 learners started

reducing after 2 years. The way of learning, therefore, determines the kind of knowledge developed, with receptive learning leading to higher receptive knowledge and productive to greater productive vocabulary knowledge (Griffin & Harley, 1996; Mondria & Wiersma, 2004). Just encountering the words does not seem to matter so much as encountering it in meaningful contexts (Laufer & Paribakht, 1998).

The type of high school attended significantly influences the eventual quality and quantity of vocabulary knowledge. Castro-Garcia (2020) conducted a comparative study on students from three types of high schools: (a) content-based, (b) semi-private, and (c) private. The findings of the study revealed that the number of instruction hours directly correlated with an increase in students' productive vocabulary knowledge, with students from the content-based instruction high school outperforming their peers. Similarly, a longer duration of language learning, resulting in more teaching hours, is anticipated to significantly enhance students' vocabulary knowledge. Such analyses have not yet been conducted in Bosnia and Herzegovina, where proficiency in English is highly valued, greatly enhancing academic and career prospects (Brdarević-Čeljo, 2024; Brdarević-Čeljo, Ahmetović & Bajić, 2021; Brdarević-Čeljo, Bećirović & Dubravac, 2021; Dedović-Atilla & Dubravac, 2022; Dubravac et al., 2018; Dubravac & Latić, 2019; Latić & Dubravac, 2019). Therefore, insights leading to more effective language learning would be exceptionally beneficial in this EFL context.

Another factor that might influence the relationship is the choice of instruments, i.e., whether free or controlled productive vocabulary knowledge is targeted. There are some indications (Laufer, 1998) that while the association might exist between receptive and controlled productive knowledge, it could be absent in case of receptive and free productive knowledge. Moreover, the current students' proficiency level might exert an impact on the relationship between the two types of vocabulary knowledge. However, while some show that the gap between them narrows down as learners become more proficient (Laufer & Paribakht, 1998; Morgan & Oberdeck, 1930; Zhong & Hirsh, 2009), others suggest it widens with progress in learning (Laufer, 1998), which might be probably assigned to the way in which language is learned, and the presence of incidental learning. The current study will further contribute to understanding these issues, comparing students' receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge at 2000-, 3000- and 5000-word frequency levels. Taking into consideration the association between these two types of vocabulary knowledge and different factors, such as students' official grade level and their self-rated grade, the type of high school completed, and the length of official EFL learning, the research will provide useful and clear guidelines on how to create an environment conducive to greater vocabulary knowledge overall, as well as receptive and

productive vocabulary development, in particular. Therefore, the study is guided by the following research questions:

- (1) What is the level of receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge among first-year university students in Bosnia and Herzegovina?
- (2) Does the level of students' receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge vary with respect to their self-rated EFL proficiency?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge and students' English GPA, school type, and the length of EFL learning?

3. Method

A quantitative method was employed in this research. A survey was used to collect the data, which were entered into the *Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS)* version 25.0. The normality test was carried out (cf. Byrne, 2010; Chua, 2013; Hair et al., 2010) prior to conducting statistical tests used to answer the research questions.

3.1. Participants

Table 1 (below) displays details about the current study participants, chosen by the convenience sampling method. 278 of them ($N = 278$) took part in this study, 152 (54.6%) female and 126 (45.3%) male students with the age range from 18 to 25. In terms of their self-rated English proficiency, 68 claimed to have basic knowledge of English necessary for basic daily communication, 70 to have intermediate knowledge which enables them to communicate but with many mistakes, 89 considered to have upper intermediate knowledge being able to use English in many situations without many mistakes, and 51 claimed to be able to use English without any difficulties. When it comes to their official GPA, they were asked to give both elementary and high school average grade, which were combined and the mean was calculated. Thus, 24 of them had the GPA of 3 during elementary and high school, 39 had 3.5, 52 had 4 while 163 had the highest average grades, 4.5 or 5. The majority of our participants (38.8%) finished Gymnasium, 70 finished Technical and 28 Medical high school. Other high schools were grouped together, and there were students who had finished different religious high schools, high school of economics, or some international high schools. Since English is the first foreign language taught in our elementary and high schools, it is not surprising that they all had learnt it for at least 5 years. Depending on the grade of elementary school in which English was introduced, we made two groups of students based on years of studying English, 5 to 11 years and 12 and more years.

Table 1
Participants' Demography

Criteria		N	%
Self-rated EFL proficiency	Elementary	68	24.4
	Intermediate	70	25.3
	Upper intermediate	89	32.0
	Advanced	51	18.3
Students' average elementary and high school English GPA	3	24	8.6
	3.5	39	14
	4	52	18.7
	4.5	31	11.2
	5	132	47.5
Type of high school	Gymnasium	108	38.8
	Medical high school	28	10.1
	Technical high school	70	25.2
	Other	72	25.9
Length of learning English	5 to 11 years	170	61.2
	12 and more	108	38.8

3.2. Materials

Receptive vocabulary knowledge was measured by a *Receptive Vocabulary Levels Test* (Nation, 1983; Schmitt et al., 2001) with a word-definition matching format. The students were given 18 words per three levels of word frequency, 2000-, 3000- and 5000-word levels, clustered in six groups. The students were presented with 6 words in a column on the left and corresponding meanings for three out of those six words in the column on the right and asked to match each meaning sense on the right with a single word offered on the left. Each cluster is, thus, focused on three words, even though the students should be familiar with the other three words to be able to eliminate them (Read, 1988).

Productive vocabulary knowledge test was also based on a *Vocabulary Levels Test*. It was measured by the means of a *Test of Controlled Productive Ability* (Laufer & Nation, 1999) in which for each item, students were given a meaningful sentence with the first letters of the target word provided to eliminate the use of possible alternatives. Thus, they were prevented from using another word which might fit well in the sentence, but might belong to the other level based on its frequency of occurrence. The test comprised 18 items at three levels, namely 2000-, 3000- and 5000-word levels. Table 2 shows that the reliability coefficients were all around .9, indicating that the

instrument is internally consistent. The normality tests confirmed the data are normally distributed (cf. Hair et al., 2010).

Table 2
Reliability and Normality Statistics

Scale	Cronbach's alpha	Skewness		Kurtosis	
		Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Receptive 2000 level	.910	-.956	.146	-.053	.291
Receptive 3000 level	.924	-.812	.146	-.429	.291
Receptive 5000 level	.933	-.198	.146	-1.296	.291
Productive 2000 level	.940	-.052	.146	-1.464	.291
Productive 3000 level	.916	.631	.146	-.819	.291
Productive 5000 level	.896	.697	.146	-.835	.291

3.3. Procedure

Following the acquisition of proper informed consent from both university administrators and participants, ensuring anonymity, confidentiality, and the voluntary nature of the participation in this study, the researchers distributed the vocabulary tests. The participants received comprehensive explanations about the instrument, and they were informed about the research objectives. Subsequently, they took the vocabulary tests, the receptive test followed by the productive test. It took them approximately 35 minutes to complete the tests.

4. Results

As for the students' overall receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge, the participants' mean scores on the receptive vocabulary knowledge measure was $M = 12.4$, while the mean score on the productive vocabulary measure was $M = 6.20$, with the maximum possible score on both being 18. Specifically, receptive knowledge scores ranged from $M = 9.94$ at the 5000-frequency level to $M = 13.95$ at the 2000 frequency level. For the productive knowledge test, the participants achieved the following scores: $M = 4.45$ at the 5000-frequency level, $M = 5.38$ at the 3000-frequency level, and $M = 8.78$ at the 2000 frequency level. Notably, the smallest gap between receptive and productive scores occurred at the 2000 frequency level, while the largest discrepancy was observed between the scores at the 3000 frequency level.

Receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge among students with different levels of self-rated EL knowledge was also investigated. Descriptive statistics shows that the advanced group outperformed all other groups on all the measures ($M = 16.5$ on the receptive and $M = 11.5$ on the productive knowledge test). In fact, the scores corresponded to the self-rated levels. Thus,

the group that claimed to have only elementary knowledge showed the lowest level of knowledge ($M = 7.86$ on the receptive and $M = 1.64$ on the productive knowledge test), followed by intermediate ($M = 11.3$ at the receptive and $M = 4.67$ on the productive knowledge test) and upper-intermediate groups ($M = 14.5$ on the receptive and $M = 8.04$ on the productive knowledge test). As a rule, receptive knowledge was higher than productive, and, interestingly, the difference between these two types of knowledge was greater among students with lower levels of self-rated ELF proficiency, while this gap narrowed as their proficiency level was higher (see Appendix A).

A one-way multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted to determine whether any of the aforementioned differences were statistically significant, and the results confirmed significant differences in receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge between students with different levels of self-rated EL knowledge [Wilks' $\Lambda = .413$, $F(18, 761) = 15.6$, $p < .001$, multivariate $\eta^2 = .255$]. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted on each dependent variable as a follow-up test to MANOVA and the differences in self-rated English knowledge proved to be significant for all receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge frequency levels, namely receptive vocabulary 2000-word frequency level [$F(3, 274) = 64.9$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .415$], receptive vocabulary 3000-word frequency level [$F(3, 274) = 56.2$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .381$], receptive vocabulary 5000-word frequency level [$F(3, 274) = 65.3$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .417$], productive vocabulary 2000-word frequency level [$F(3, 274) = 95.9$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .512$], productive vocabulary 3000-word frequency level [$F(3, 274) = 67.7$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .426$] and productive vocabulary 5000-word frequency level [$F(3, 274) = 65.3$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .417$]. The Bonferroni post hoc analysis revealed significant differences in receptive vocabulary at the 2000-word and 3000-word frequency levels among all groups except upper-intermediate and advanced groups. In addition to this, there was a significant difference between all groups in receptive knowledge at 5000-word frequency level as well as in productive knowledge at all word frequency levels, i.e., 2000-word, 3000-word and 5000-word frequency levels.

Receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge based on (a) students' GPA, (b) the type of school they attended, and (c) the amount of time spent on learning English was also investigated. Mean values based on the average English grade in elementary and high school (Appendix B) confirm that the most successful group was the one with the highest average grade (means in the range from $M = 16.12$ to $M = 12.92$ on the receptive, and from $M = 12.74$ to $M = 6.77$ on the productive knowledge test), closely followed by the group with the second highest grade (means in the range from $M = 15.17$ to $M = 9.27$ on the receptive, and from $M = 8.33$ to $M = 4.57$ on the productive knowledge test).

However, the group with the average grade 3.00 (means in the range from $M = 11.64$ to $M = 8.10$ on the receptive, and from $M = 5.87$ to $M = 2.84$ on the productive knowledge test) was better than the group with the average grade 3.50 (means in the range from $M = 10.32$ to $M = 6.24$ on the receptive, and from $M = 3.12$ to $M = 1.30$ on the productive knowledge test and 4.00 (means in the range from $M = 12.24$ to $M = 6.85$ on the receptive, and from $M = 5.36$ to $M = 2.30$ on the productive knowledge test) on almost all of the measures. Descriptive statistics based on the type of high school (Appendix C) revealed that Gymnasium students were the most successful, while the difference between them and other students was more profound on productive than on receptive knowledge tests. In terms of the length of learning English, the same trend is noticed in both groups—higher receptive than productive knowledge, and the lower the frequency of words, the lower the knowledge (Appendix D). However, the group that has learned English for more than twelve years (means in the range from $M = 15.61$ to $M = 12.06$ on the receptive, and from $M = 11.37$ to $M = 6.15$ on the productive knowledge test) outscored the other group (means in the range from $M = 13.09$ to $M = 8.77$ on the receptive, and from $M = 7.38$ to $M = 3.6$ on the productive knowledge test) on all of the tests.

MANOVA showed an insignificant interaction effect of GPA X, School type X the length of learning EFL as well as GPA X School type, School type X the length of learning EFL and GPA X the length of learning EFL on combined dependent variables of receptive and productive vocabulary. However, there was a significant main effect of GPA [Wilks' $\Lambda = .625$, $F(28, 916) = 4.05$, $p < .001$, multivariate $\eta^2 = .104$] and school type [Wilks' $\Lambda = .858$, $F(21, 649) = 1.67$, $p = .027$, multivariate $\eta^2 = .050$] and an insignificant main effect of the length of learning EFL [Wilks' $\Lambda = .972$, $F(7, 226) = .936$, $p = .479$, multivariate $\eta^2 = .028$].

ANOVA as a follow-up test to MANOVA revealed significant differences for all dependent variables based on GPA, i.e., receptive vocabulary at 2000-word frequency level [$F(4, 232) = 8.69$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .130$], receptive vocabulary at 3000-word frequency level [$F(4, 232) = 9.21$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .137$], receptive vocabulary at 5000-word frequency level [$F(4, 232) = 8.12$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .123$], productive vocabulary at 2000-word frequency level [$F(4, 232) = 20.1$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .257$], productive vocabulary at 3000-word frequency level [$F(4, 232) = 12.9$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .181$] and productive vocabulary at 5000-word frequency level [$F(4, 232) = 12.6$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .159$]. The Bonferroni post hoc test showed significant differences in receptive vocabulary 2000-word frequency level between students whose GPA is 3.00 and 4.50 and 3.00 and 5.00, respectively. As for the group of students whose GPA is 3.50, the differences were significant for receptive vocabulary 2000-word frequency level in their comparison with the groups with GPA 4.50 and 5.00. Students with GPA 4.00 significantly differ from those

with GPA 4.00 and 5.00. As for receptive vocabulary at the 2000-word frequency level, a significant difference was found between students with GPA 3.00 and 5.00, 3.50 and 4.50 and 5.00, then 4.00 and 5.00 and 4.50 and 5.00, respectively. Concerning the receptive vocabulary at 5000-word level, the difference was significant between students with GPA 3.00 and 5.00; 3.50 and 5.00; 4.00 and 5.00 and 4.50 and 5.00, respectively. As for the productive vocabulary 2000-word frequency level, the difference was significant between students with GPA 3.00 and 5.00; 3.50 and 4.50 and 3.50 and 5.00; 4.00 and 5.00 and 4.50 and 5.00. In regard to productive vocabulary 3000-word frequency level, the difference was significant between students with GPA 3.00 and 5.00; 3.50 and 4.50 and 3.50 and 5.00; 4.00 and 5.00. and 4.50 and 5.00, respectively. As for the productive vocabulary 5000-word frequency level, the difference was significant between students with GPA 3.00 and 5.00; 3.50 and 4.50 and 3.50 and 5.00; 4.00 and 5.00. and 4.50 and 5.00.

ANOVA as a follow-up test to MANOVA showed significant differences in students' receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge based on the type of school they attended, i.e., receptive vocabulary 2000-word frequency level [$F(3, 232) = 3.97, p = .009$, partial $\eta^2 = .049$], receptive vocabulary 3000-word frequency level [$F(3, 232) = 5.91, p = .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .071$], receptive vocabulary 5000-word frequency level [$F(3, 232) = 3.65, p = .013$, partial $\eta^2 = .045$], productive vocabulary 2000-word frequency level [$F(3, 232) = 4.79, p = .003$, partial $\eta^2 = .058$]. However, there was no significant difference in productive vocabulary knowledge at 3000-word frequency level [$F(3, 232) = 1.43, p = .235$, partial $\eta^2 = .018$] and productive vocabulary knowledge at 5000-word frequency level [$F(3, 232) = 1.57, p = .197$, partial $\eta^2 = .020$]. The Bonferroni post hoc test showed significant differences in receptive vocabulary knowledge at 2000-word frequency level between the following groups of students, namely students attending other schools and medical schools, students attending Gymnasium and medical school and Gymnasium and technical school. As for the receptive vocabulary knowledge at the 3000-word frequency level, significant differences were found between students attending Gymnasium and some other schools, Gymnasium and medical and Gymnasium and technical school. Significant differences were also found in the students' receptive vocabulary at the 5000-word frequency level between students attending other schools and technical schools as well as between students attending Gymnasium and medical, and Gymnasium and technical, school. As for students' productive vocabulary knowledge, the Bonferroni post hoc test showed significant differences in the 2000-word frequency level between students attending Gymnasium and all other groups. The same was noticed for students who attended some of the high schools grouped together and named 'other high schools'—these students showed significantly different knowledge from students who finished Gymnasium, technical or medical high school. On

the other hand, the difference between medical and technical schools proved to be insignificant. Concerning productive vocabulary knowledge at the 3000-word frequency level, a significant difference was found between students who finished 'other high schools' and those who finished Gymnasium, medical or technical high school. As for productive vocabulary knowledge at the 5000-word frequency level, a significant difference was found between students attending Gymnasium and medical and Gymnasium and technical schools.

5. Discussion

As for overall receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge, the current study showed that our participants have passive knowledge of 77.7% of words belonging to the 2000 frequency level group, 72.2% of those in the group of 3000 most frequent words, and 55.2% of those in the group of 5000 frequency level words. However, the scores are much lower in terms of productive vocabulary knowledge. Thus, they demonstrated the knowledge of 49.3% of the words in the 2000 frequency level group, 29.8% of those in the 3000-frequency level group and 24.7% of those in the 5000 frequency level group. Thus, it is evident that the participants' receptive knowledge exceeds their productive knowledge, which is aligned with the results reported in numerous previous studies (Fan, 2000; Hajiyeva, 2014; Laufer, 1998; Laufer & Goldstein, 2004; Laufer & Paribakht, 1998; Lee, 2024; Melka, 1997; Tschirner, 2004; Waring, 1998; Webb, 2008; Zhong & Hirsh, 2009). Moreover, the findings suggested that receptive knowledge is around double the size of productive knowledge, which is in accordance with Eringa (1974) but in contrast with some studies (e.g., Hajiyeva, 2014; Morgan & Oberdeck, 1930) which reported a much larger gap between these two types of vocabulary knowledge. This might be attributed to the use of controlled productive vocabulary knowledge test. In fact, it has been indicated that a greater difference might arise if a free productive vocabulary knowledge test is used (Laufer, 1998). Also, as Fan (2000) proposed, a smaller gap between receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge exists if students are exposed to English outside school, which seems to be the case here as shown in numerous studies conducted in this context (e.g., Brdarević-Čeljo & Dubravac, 2022; Brdarević-Čeljo et al., 2023; Dedović-Atilla & Dubravac, 2022; Dubravac & Latić, 2019; Latić & Dubravac, 2019; Ribo & Dubravac, 2021). However, as students learning English outside formal educational environment are rather passively exposed to English, if we want their productive knowledge to be greater, more attention should be paid to active language use within schools as it leads to productive knowledge development (Griffin & Harley, 1996; Mondria & Wiersma, 2004; Šišková, 2016). Interestingly, the largest gap between receptive and productive knowledge was noticed for the words at the 3000 frequency level. This shows that students might have encountered these words in materials they are

exposed to, as the mean is 13.26 but have not had frequent opportunities to use them actively, with the $M = 5.38$ on the productive knowledge measure. On the other hand, both receptive and productive knowledge of the words at the 5000 frequency level are relatively low, the former still being double the size of the latter. Students need a lot of passive and active language practice to acquire these words. It appears that in the active language use during elementary and high school students mostly rely on the most frequent words.

Receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge among different levels of self-rated EL knowledge were also investigated. When it comes to the influence of various factors, firstly, the impact of self-rated knowledge was evaluated, and it proved significant at all levels of both receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge. The participants who claimed to have only elementary English knowledge necessary for basic communication achieved the lowest scores on all measures, while those who reported having a solid knowledge with mistakes in communication, those who could communicate easily without many mistakes and those who claimed to use English fluently scored better on all measures in accordance with their self-rated level of EFL knowledge. No difference was observed between two most proficient groups on the measure of receptive knowledge at the 2000-word and 3000-word frequency levels. Therefore, we can conclude that one's self-assessment is well based on vocabulary knowledge, and even more on active than on passive knowledge, which confirms a strong relationship between vocabulary knowledge and overall language proficiency (Masrai & Milton, 2021; Waring & Nation, 2004).

As for receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge based on students' GPA, the type of school they attend, and time spent learning English, the role of vocabulary knowledge in the overall language proficiency was further confirmed by investigating the relationship between English GPA and vocabulary knowledge. It means that both types of knowledge are taken into account when grading students. However, we can also see that the standards to be achieved are not so high, as those most successful students demonstrated receptive knowledge of around 89% of words from the 2000-word frequency level group, around 88% of those from the 3000-word frequency level group and 72% of those from the 5000-word frequency level group. In terms of productive knowledge, they confirmed the active use of around 70% of the words from the 2000-, 46% of those from the 3000-, and around 38% of those from the 5000-word frequency lists. Thus, the focus seems to be more on receptive than on productive knowledge, although the most highly graded group scored the best results in all the categories. We can conclude that students with the highest grade 5 can easily understand materials in English, but cannot produce them easily. Those with lower grades are expected to face difficulties even in understanding authentic materials. We also see that even in the group of most successful students, productive knowledge does not exceed

receptive knowledge, confirming that receptive precedes productive (Aitchison, 1994; Channell, 1988; Melka, 1997), and even though at higher proficiency levels it is marked by faster development, it never reaches productive knowledge. Interestingly, the group with the average grade 3 outscored the one with average grade 3.5 and sometimes even the one with 4.00, which might be attributed to the attention given to grammar knowledge when grading students, as these students might have better grammar knowledge than those who showed better vocabulary knowledge. Interestingly, the gap between receptive and productive knowledge seems to be smaller among more successful learners and greater among those with lower English GPA just as suggested in some previous studies (Laufer & Paribakht, 1998; Lee, 2024; Morgan & Oberdeck, 1930; Zhong & Hirsh, 2009). However, this study also showed that the same might be claimed when students' self-assessed knowledge is considered.

In terms of the type of high school students graduated from, it also proved to be a significant factor. Although all students are equally exposed to English outside school, formal English education seems to play a relevant role in their overall vocabulary knowledge. In fact, some previous studies conducted in this specific EFL context have emphasized great opportunities for English learning outside schools (Brdarević-Čeljo & Dubravac, 2022; Dedović-Atilla & Dubravac, 2022; Dubravac, 2016; Dubravac & Skopljak, 2019; Skopljak & Dubravac, 2019). However, we still notice that formal education should be carefully considered as it makes a difference as already indicated in the study by Castro-Garcia (2020). Those students who finished Gymnasium and had up to three hours of English a week outperformed all other students on all the tests. Students attending other high schools, including religious high school, international high school, high school of economics, closely followed those participants who completed Gymnasium, which might be addressed to additional English classes some of them offer. Thus, in international high schools most classes are held in English and in religious high school students can choose to attend a special English language program where most of the classes are held in English. Medical and Technical high schools offer pretty similar chances for English learning, and therefore, their students demonstrate a similar level of vocabulary knowledge. We see that education can help a lot in shaping future workforce, which definitely need competence in English (Dedović-Atilla & Dubravac, 2022). Thus, better results might be expected introducing higher number of teaching hours and combining formal and informal language learning (Dubravac & Brdarević-Čeljo, 2024).

In addition to more teaching hours, earlier introduction in educational institutions is desirable. Although there was no significant difference between those who learned English for 5 to 11 years and those who learned it for more than 12 years, we notice that higher scores on all the tests were achieved by

those who learned it longer. It might be that most of the students in the first group learned English around 10 years, which made them more similar to those who learned it for 12 and more years. The difference might have been statistically significant if a greater difference between the groups had existed, which might be a limitation of the present study and at the same time the suggestion for forthcoming studies.

The other limitation of the current study might be the inexistence of qualitative research as a support for quantitative research. Through it, further details about developing vocabulary might have been found out. Also, both free and controlled productive knowledge tests might have been used to give a more comprehensive overview of the situation.

6. Conclusion

Vocabulary knowledge presents a significant aspect of one's overall language proficiency, and, thus, should be carefully considered. Both teachers and students are aware of its importance, and attach immense significance to it when assessing overall language proficiency. This study confirmed a significant relationship between vocabulary knowledge and both self-rated knowledge and EFL GPA during elementary and high school, with p values being lower than .001. Therefore, different layers of vocabulary knowledge should be further explored if we aim at effective language use. We notice that learners' passive, i.e., receptive knowledge, well exceeds their active, i.e., productive vocabulary knowledge. Therefore, much practice requiring active language use is necessary to make that passive knowledge active, to move from passive recognition to active recall. Moreover, much more attention during high school should be paid to less frequent vocabulary. Elementary school should equip learners with the most frequent words, and then those belonging to 5000 and 10,000 most frequent words should be the focus. Of course, all this should be combined with effective teaching methods applied and suitable materials used. Students should be taught effective vocabulary learning strategies so that they can pursue their vocabulary development individually throughout their lifetime. Only in such a way can we expect desired outcomes—when learners have good basis, have developed awareness of the importance of both quality and quantity of vocabulary knowledge, and have necessary skills to continue their language learning process on their own, in and out of educational institutions.

Authors' Statement

Vildana Dubravac and Amna Brdarević-Čeljo wrote the introduction, background, discussion, and conclusion sections. Senad Bećirović wrote the methodology and results sections.

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Appendix A: Means and One-way Analyses of Variances in Receptive and Productive Vocabulary Knowledge and Self-Rated EFL Proficiency

	Elementary	Intermediate	Upper intermediate	Advanced	$F(3,274)$	η^2
Receptive						
2000 level	9.64	13.40	16.20	17.00	64.9**	.415
3000 level	8.89	12.20	15.40	17.20	56.2**	.381
5000 level	5.05	8.20	12.08	15.50	65.3**	.417
Productive						
2000 level	2.73	6.92	11.60	14.80	95.9**	.512
3000 level	1.15	4.06	6.88	10.05	67.7**	.426
5000 level	1.04	3.01	5.63	9.07	65.3**	.417

** $p < .001$ **Appendix B: Means and One-Way Analyses of Variances in Receptive and Productive Vocabulary Knowledge and English GPA**

	3.00	3.50	4.00	4.50	5.00	$F(4,323)$	η^2
Receptive							
2000 level	11.64	10.32	12.24	15.17	16.12	8.69**	.130
3000 level	11.39	9.27	11.35	13.17	15.82	9.21**	.137
5000 level	8.10	6.24	6.85	9.27	12.92	8.12**	.123
Productive							
2000 level	5.87	3.12	5.36	8.33	12.74	20.1**	.257
3000 level	3.16	1.51	2.63	5.37	8.32	12.9**	.181
5000 level	2.84	1.30	2.30	4.57	6.77	12.6**	.159

** $p < .001$ **Appendix C: Means and One-Way Analyses of Variances in Receptive and Productive Vocabulary Knowledge and the Type of High School**

	Other	Gym	Medical	Technical	$F(3,232)$	p	η^2
Receptive							
2000 level	14.16	15.48	12.06	12.60	3.97	.009	.049
3000 level	13.23	15.14	11.50	11.52	5.91	.001	.071
5000 level	10.25	11.81	8.12	7.81	3.65	.013	.045
Productive							
2000 level	9.08	11.12	6.42	6.30	4.79	.003	.058
3000 level	5.64	6.99	3.72	3.83	1.43	.235	.018
5000 level	4.62	5.85	3.25	3.07	1.57	.197	.020

Appendix D: Descriptive Statistics for the Groups Based on the Length of Learning English